

Self-Supervised Market-State Embeddings for Demand-Response Window Design: Evidence from Czech Republic and Greece Electricity Markets

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Abstract

Demand-response (DR) programs depend on timely identification of high-price and high-ramping periods, yet conventional threshold-based methods trigger alerts only once extreme conditions have already materialized. This study proposes a state-aware DR framework based on self-supervised market-state embeddings, learned from joint sequences of load, forecast, and day-ahead price data from the Czech Republic and Greece (2021–2024). The model captures latent market regimes without supervision and converts them into DR alert scores calibrated using distribution-free conformal methods to guarantee risk levels under non-stationarity. Results show a clear performance trade-off: static thresholds achieve the highest precision for the most extreme events (hit-rate@5% up to 1.0), while state-aware alerts provide substantially earlier warnings, improving mean lead-time by +2.5 hours for price spikes and +1.3 hours for ramp events. Cross-market evaluation demonstrates 46–214% transfer retention, indicating that learned states generalize across countries and reflect structural similarities in European electricity systems. Conformal calibration maintains coverage close to nominal guarantees across years, strengthening operational reliability. Overall, the proposed approach offers a practical and transferable pathway for enhancing anticipatory DR scheduling, with the potential to support flexibility activation in increasingly renewable and volatile power systems.

Keywords: Demand Response; Self-Supervised Learning; Market-State Embeddings; Conformal Prediction; Early Warning; Electricity Markets; Renewable Energy Integration; Power Systems

1 Introduction

The rapid expansion of variable renewable energy (VRE), particularly wind and solar, has increased volatility and uncertainty in European power systems. Because these resources are

34 intermittent, their large-scale integration creates challenges for grid stability, ramping events, and
35 market efficiency. Demand response (DR) has therefore become an essential operational tool. It
36 enables flexible loads to adjust consumption in response to system conditions, which improves
37 the balance between supply and demand [1]. In regions like Spain and Ireland, system operators
38 are exploring methods to ensure VRE integration supports grid stability by implementing
39 centralized controls or adapting grid codes [2]. Moreover, advanced energy storage systems are
40 essential for managing the high variability of renewables, further complementing demand-side
41 resources [3]. These efforts highlight that DR is a critical source of flexibility and that it can
42 reduce curtailment of renewable generation and strengthen overall system resilience [4].

43 This study focuses on two contrasting European electricity markets: the Czech Republic
44 (CZ), which is transitioning from coal to renewables and has limited interconnection, and Greece
45 (GR), which has high solar penetration and islanded subsystems. Recent analysis of cooling and
46 solar resource conditions in Athens confirms the strength and stability of Greek solar availability,
47 which reinforces the importance of flexible demand tools in high-solar systems [5]. Recent
48 evidence also shows that Czech decarbonisation will substantially increase the need for
49 flexibility services. Long-term sector-coupling modelling estimates that flexible CHP and
50 Power-to-Heat technologies could quadruple balancing reserve provision by 2030–2050,
51 underscoring the growing importance of system-level flexibility mechanisms such as DR timing
52 [6]. The Czech energy transition is also shaped by structural challenges at the municipal level.
53 Recent evidence shows that community renewable energy projects face fragmented governance,
54 limited local capacity, and diverse value proposition models, which slow the deployment of
55 distributed renewables and highlight the need for system-level flexibility solutions such as DR
56 [7]. By analyzing market data from 2021 to 2024, we evaluate whether latent market states can
57 be discovered and used to improve the timing of DR windows across different system contexts.

58 **1.1 Existing approaches and their limitations**

59 Most DR research concentrates on identifying which customers are likely to respond to dynamic
60 tariffs by using smart meter features. For example, Shi and Jiao cluster daily load profiles and
61 compute volatility and peak–valley indicators to classify household DR capacity. They achieve
62 approximately 65 to 75 % accuracy in identifying DR potential under high- and low-price events
63 [8]. Similarly, Wang et al. extract a large set of time- and frequency-domain indicators from Irish
64 CER smart meter data. They use semi-supervised learning to identify flexible consumers,
65 showing that limited labels can still support accurate classification [9]. These studies focus on
66 identifying who is flexible but do not determine when system-level DR actions should occur.

67 Recent work has also applied self-supervised learning to electricity market data.
68 Papadopoulos et al. show that self-supervised encoders can extract informative representations
69 from electricity price sequences and improve day-ahead price forecasting accuracy. Their study
70 confirms the usefulness of self-supervised objectives for energy time-series analysis, although
71 their focus remains on forecasting rather than on the timing of DR windows [10].

72 Recent European evidence also indicates that DR awareness among small users is low,
73 although willingness to participate is high once incentives are clearly explained. Users express a
74 preference for predictable incentive programs and transparent participation rules [11]. This
75 suggests that system-level timing tools must be aligned with both technical needs and user
76 participation requirements.

77 **1.2 The research gap in system-level DR timing**

78 Most advanced DR research focuses on customer-level behavior, while far fewer methods
79 address when DR should be activated at the system level. System operators still rely heavily on
80 static threshold rules, such as price exceeding a percentile or load/price ramps crossing a fixed
81 level. These rules are inherently reactive: they typically trigger only after extreme conditions
82 have already begun, leaving little room for anticipatory actions.

83 A further challenge is that electricity markets are highly non-stationary. Weather variability,
84 fuel-price shocks, renewable penetration, and evolving market policies all contribute to frequent
85 distribution shifts. Recent studies show that conformal prediction can retain valid coverage and
86 deliver trading value under such shifts in day-ahead and balancing markets [12]. Evidence from
87 Nordic balancing markets confirms that imbalance prices respond strongly to forecast errors,
88 design changes and shifting system conditions. These patterns are not visible from day-ahead
89 price alone. This reinforces that DR timing should be informed by underlying market states, not
90 simple price triggers [13].

91 Price spikes can also send misleading signals. Fleschutz et al. show that price-based DR may
92 unintentionally increase carbon emissions in several European countries because coal and lignite
93 often set marginal prices [14]. Intraday market studies further reveal asymmetric and clustered
94 price risks shaped by renewable fluctuations, demand stress, and shocks transmitted from day-
95 ahead markets, and these conditions cannot be captured by static thresholds[15].

96 Flexible-demand studies likewise indicate that price-only signals are insufficient for optimal
97 DR activation. Rens et al. demonstrate that load allocation depends on uncertainty and risk costs,
98 implying DR decisions should account for the uncertainty structure of market dynamics rather
99 than absolute price levels [16]. Integrated market-clearing models, such as those by Koltsaklis
100 and Knápek, show that distributed resources can provide substantial balancing services across
101 coupled systems. However, these frameworks still assume that operators know when flexibility
102 should be scheduled, rather than learning stress regimes directly from market data [17].

103 Recent machine-learning work has improved device-level and building-level optimization,
104 including load disaggregation, demand-side management, and joint storage–HVAC control
105 [18,19]. Additional studies have examined gas-to-power spillovers during stressed periods [20].
106 These contributions provide valuable insights but do not address the system-level question of
107 when DR should be initiated.

108 **1.3 Contributions of this work**

109 This study addresses these research gaps through three main contributions:

- 110 1. We introduce a self-supervised learning pipeline that extracts electricity market state
111 embeddings directly from joint price and load sequences.
- 112 2. We define a state-aware DR scoring framework that incorporates conformal risk control
113 to maintain reliable coverage under non-stationary market conditions.
- 114 3. We provide a cross-market transfer evaluation using data from CZ and GR from 2021 to
115 2024 to demonstrate robustness and generalization across contrasting system profiles.

116
117 The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews background concepts
118 and related work. Section 3 presents the methodology, including data processing, window

119 construction, self-supervised embedding, DR scoring, and conformal calibration. Section 4
120 reports empirical results on market-state discovery, DR detection accuracy, lead-time
121 performance, cross-market transferability, and reliability under risk control. Section 5 discusses
122 key insights and limitations. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

123 **2 Literature Review**

124 Demand-response (DR) research includes consumer flexibility identification, electricity price
125 and load forecasting, and the use of representation learning for temporal energy data. However,
126 only a limited number of studies examine how to determine the best timing for system-level DR
127 activation. This section summarizes the most relevant literature and clarifies the position of this
128 study.

129 **2.1 Demand-response targeting: identifying who can respond**

130 Previous DR work has focused mainly on assessing the flexibility of households and individual
131 consumers. Shi and Jiao [8] cluster typical electricity consumption profiles and apply machine-
132 learning classifiers to estimate DR potential. Their results achieve 65 to 75 % accuracy for high-
133 price and low-price conditions. Wang et al. [9] analyze Irish CER smart-meter data and use a
134 semi-supervised learning approach to classify flexible users. Their method achieves strong
135 accuracy even when only a small share of samples is labeled. Recent work also studies demand
136 response in coupled power and transportation networks. Bai et al. [21] propose a battery charging
137 and swapping system that coordinates charging schedules and logistics routes using time-of-use
138 tariffs and congestion prices, which illustrates how demand response concepts extend to electric
139 vehicle infrastructure and multi-network operation. Recent work has introduced causal artificial
140 intelligence frameworks that estimate prosumer DR participation through counterfactual
141 analysis, enabling utilities to assess behavior under unobserved price or program scenarios
142 without needing experimental control groups [22]. Logistic regression models have also been
143 used to classify DR participation from household features and consumption patterns. For
144 example, Mahmud et al. [23] analyze demographic and load characteristics to predict binary DR
145 participation, which reinforces the importance of consumer-level flexibility modelling.
146 Behavioral and program design factors also influence household DR participation. Sridhar et al.
147 [24] show that enrolment decisions depend on perceived benefits, salesperson engagement, and
148 socio-economic characteristics, reinforcing the importance of consumer-level flexibility
149 assessment.

150 These studies concentrate on identifying which users are suitable for participation. They do
151 not address the system-level decision regarding the best moment to activate DR. As a result,
152 many operators still rely on simple rules such as price thresholds or ramp thresholds, which often
153 react only after extreme conditions have already been developed.

154 **2.2 Electricity price and load forecasting and system** 155 **modelling**

156 Electricity price and load forecasting has developed through classical statistical models,
157 machine-learning algorithms, and deep-learning architectures. These models are useful for
158 scheduling and bidding, but most of them focus on the prediction of a single variable. They do
159 not capture the joint behaviour of prices, residual load, renewable generation, and other
160 interacting factors that influence the value of DR actions.

161 Several system-level studies highlight the need for flexibility as the share of variable
162 renewable energy increases. Sinsel et al. [2] and Rouholamini et al. [3] show that large quantities
163 of wind and solar power create volatility and operational uncertainty. Forecast accuracy is also
164 critical for DR scheduling in smaller power systems. Electricity price forecasting has been
165 comprehensively reviewed by Lago et al. [25]. Their findings show that many studies use short
166 evaluation periods, inconsistent feature sets, and limited reproducibility, which creates
167 difficulties when comparing models across markets. Kabalci et al. [26] propose a fault detection
168 and correction framework that improves short-term load forecasts before DR-based dispatch,
169 highlighting the operational risks associated with inaccurate forecasts. Koltsaklis and Knápek
170 [17] model storage, electric vehicles, and DR within multi-area market clearing. Their model
171 captures important interactions but the timing of DR actions is still pre-defined rather than
172 learned from market data. Overall, these studies reveal the lack of tools that characterize the
173 combined evolution of price and load conditions that determine when DR is most effective.

174 **2.3 Self-supervised representation learning for energy time** 175 **series**

176 Self-supervised learning (SSL) has become a powerful technique for learning temporal
177 representations without labels. Contrastive learning and context-based representation learning
178 have shown strong performance in forecasting, anomaly detection, and behaviour analysis.
179 Papadopoulos et al. [10] demonstrate that SSL encoders improve day-ahead price forecasting
180 compared to fully-supervised baselines. Zhao et al. [16] shows that temporal SSL improves
181 forecasting robustness when data distributions shift. Although SSL is increasingly used in energy
182 research, its application is mostly limited to improving predictive accuracy. Deep generative
183 models have been used to learn latent structure in renewable time series without explicit
184 statistical assumptions, showing the value of representation learning for non-linear and non-
185 stationary energy data [27]. Prior work does not use SSL to discover operational market states
186 that can directly guide the timing of DR actions. This gap motivates the approach used in the
187 present study.

188 **2.4 Risk control and uncertainty modelling in power** 189 **markets**

190 Electricity markets are highly non-stationary due to changes in renewable output, weather
191 conditions, and policy environments. This makes threshold-based DR rules unreliable.
192 Conformal prediction offers a distribution-free method to model uncertainty under changing
193 conditions. O'Connor et al. [12] show that conformal methods provide reliable uncertainty
194 bounds in day-ahead and balancing markets. Studies of intraday markets, including Bâra et al.
195 [15], highlight the strong influence of renewable variability and demand fluctuations on price

196 volatility. These findings support the need for decision tools that consider market states rather
197 than simple surface-level indicators. Additional evidence shows that price-based DR can
198 unintentionally increase emissions when carbon prices are low [14]. This further indicates that
199 decision rules should consider broader system stress conditions instead of relying on high prices
200 alone.

201 **2.5 Research gap and positioning**

202 Existing DR research provides valuable insights into customer flexibility, device-level
203 optimization, and market-clearing mechanisms, but it does not address the central problem of
204 timing system-level DR interventions. Prior studies typically assume that operators can specify
205 when flexibility should be activated, often through fixed rules such as price or ramp thresholds.
206 These approaches are reactive and do not adapt to evolving market conditions, limiting their
207 usefulness in non-stationary electricity systems.

208 At the same time, evidence from day-ahead, intraday, and balancing markets shows that
209 extreme events arise from latent system states, not solely from price spikes or ramp magnitudes.
210 Recent findings on non-stationarity, uncertainty-driven load allocation, and gas-to-power
211 spillovers indicate that DR timing must account for deeper market dynamics to avoid false alerts,
212 missed events, or even unintended increases in emissions. Despite these insights, there is no
213 established framework that combines:

- 214 • latent market-state learning from high-dimensional price-load dynamics,
- 215 • risk-controlled DR activation that adapts to distribution shifts, and
- 216 • cross-market evaluation to test whether timing methods generalize across heterogeneous
217 system contexts.

218 This study addresses this gap by introducing a state-aware DR timing pipeline built on self-
219 supervised representation learning and conformal risk control. The approach learns underlying
220 market regimes directly from historical price and load patterns, issues alerts based on these latent
221 conditions, and evaluates transferability between two structurally different European markets
222 (CZ and GR). In doing so, the work proposed in this paper advances DR timing from static
223 threshold rules toward data-driven, anticipatory, and robust system-level decision making.

224 **3 Methodology and Data**

225 The proposed pipeline combines self-supervised representation learning with state-aware
226 demand-response (DR) scoring and conformal risk control. The workflow proceeds through five
227 stages: data integration, preprocessing and feature construction, self-supervised state embedding,
228 DR scoring, and cross-market evaluation.

Figure 1. Overview of the proposed methodological pipeline for state-aware DR signal generation.

Figure 1 indicates the full methodological pipeline proposed in this study, starting from raw data integration and preprocessing, followed by self-supervised market-state embedding, state-aware DR scoring with conformal risk control, and finally the cross-market evaluation between CZ and GR.

3.1 Data sources and scope

Hourly system load, day-ahead load forecasts, and day-ahead market prices (EUR/MWh) from ENTSO-E and national transmission system operators (TSOs) are combined for the Czech Republic (CZ) and Greece (GR) [28]. The study period covers January 2021–December 2024. All timestamps are converted from Market Time Unit (MTU), which follows local market time with daylight-saving changes, to Coordinated Universal Time (UTC), a fixed global time standard, in order to preserve seasonal clock adjustments and prevent duplication during

244 daylight-saving transitions. After cleaning and alignment, the dataset contains 35,112 hourly
 245 observations for CZ and 35,112 for GR, corresponding to a total of 70,224 hourly samples.

246 3.2 Variables and preprocessing

247 The core variables include:

- 248 • system load and day-ahead load forecast
- 249 • day-ahead market price
- 250 • country indicator (CZ or GR)

251 Let $x_t \in \mathbb{R}^d$ denote the feature vector at hour t . Preprocessing proceeds in three steps.
 252 Cleaning removes duplicated hours created during daylight-saving transitions, and gaps shorter
 253 than two hours are forward filled. Normalization applies z-score scaling per country using
 254 statistics from the training split:

$$255 \quad \tilde{x}_t = \frac{x_t - \mu_{train}}{\sigma_{train}} \quad (1)$$

256 where μ_{train} and σ_{train} are the component-wise mean and standard deviation computed from
 257 the training data of the corresponding country, and x_t is the normalized feature vector. Feature
 258 engineering introduces short-term and daily indicators of system behavior. These include one-
 259 hour and three-hour price and load ramps, twenty-four-hour rolling means and rolling standard
 260 deviations, and the price-to-load ratio as an indicator of system tightness. Sliding windows of
 261 length $T \in [24, 48]$ hours are constructed with a time-step of one hour. Each window is formed as
 262 follows:

$$263 \quad X_t = [x_{t-T+1}, x_{t-T+2}, \dots, x_t] \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times d} \quad (2)$$

264 where X_t stacks the T consecutive feature vectors ending at hour t . Window-based
 265 processing is widely used in energy-related time-series analysis, where temporal signatures help
 266 reveal underlying operational states. Recent work demonstrates that structured temporal
 267 windows and multivariate feature sets improve clustering and representation quality in energy
 268 datasets [29]. Window-based inputs are also standard in neural time-series forecasting
 269 benchmarks that rely on fixed-length segments to learn temporal patterns [30].

270 3.3 Self-supervised market-state embeddings

271 To capture latent market behavior, we train a self-supervised encoder on unlabeled sliding
 272 windows. The encoder $f_\theta(\cdot)$ maps each window to a compact embedding vector:

$$273 \quad Z_t = f_\theta(X_t) \in \mathbb{R}^k \quad (3)$$

274 where Z_t represents the k -dimensional latent market-state embedding associated with the
 275 window ending at hour t . A contrastive learning objective increases similarity between
 276 temporally adjacent windows and decreases similarity between windows from different periods.
 277 For pairs (X_i, X_j) with label $y_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}$ indicating whether they should be treated as dissimilar
 278 ($y_{ij}=1$) or similar ($y_{ij}=0$), a margin-based contrastive loss is calculated as follows:

$$279 \quad L_{contrast} = \sum_{i,j} (1 - y_{ij}) \|Z_i - Z_j\|^2 + y_{ij} \max(0, m - \|Z_i - Z_j\|^2) \quad (4)$$

280 where m is a margin hyper-parameter. This follows the general principle of joint-embedding
 281 self-supervised learning [31]. The resulting embeddings summarize the joint dynamics of load,
 282 forecast, and price without requiring labels or explicit forecasting targets, and they provide a
 283 low-dimensional representation that can be used for downstream market-state analysis.

284 3.4 State-aware DR scoring with conformal risk control

285 Market-state embeddings are translated into DR alerts through a scalar scoring function. Let \mathbf{h}_t
286 denote a vector of engineered indicators at time t , such as volatility measures, ramp magnitudes,
287 price-to-load ratio, and indicators of state rarity. The state-aware score is given by:

$$288 \quad S_t = \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{h}_t \quad (5)$$

289 where \mathbf{w} up-weights conditions associated with high stress. A DR alert is issued when the
290 score exceeds a threshold q :

$$291 \quad \text{Alert at } t \Leftrightarrow S_t > q \quad (6)$$

292 To ensure statistical reliability, we apply conformal calibration and set q based on a held-out
293 calibration period. Let \mathcal{C} denote the set of calibration times (here 2024-H1), and define
294 nonconformity scores as follows:

$$295 \quad a_t = S_t, t \in \mathcal{C} \quad (7)$$

296 For a chosen risk level $\alpha \in (0,1)$, the calibrated threshold is given by:

$$297 \quad \hat{q}_{1-\alpha} = \inf \left\{ q: \frac{1}{|\mathcal{C}|} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{C}} (a_t > q) \leq \alpha \right\} \quad (8)$$

298 Future alerts on the test period use this calibrated threshold, i.e.:

$$299 \quad \text{Alert}_t = 1(s_t > \hat{q}_{1-\alpha}) \quad (9)$$

300 which provides approximate finite-sample control of the fraction of time steps classified as
301 high-risk under mild assumptions. Distribution-free predictive inference methods such as
302 jackknife+ provide finite-sample coverage guarantees for regression and related prediction
303 problems under minimal assumptions [32]. Recent work on conformal prediction for time series
304 shows that calibrated prediction intervals can retain valid coverage properties for stochastic and
305 potentially non-stationary sequences [33]. In our case, the calibration step, performed on 2024-
306 H1, produces alerting rules with approximate coverage guarantees that adapt to evolving market
307 conditions.

308 3.5 Cross-market evaluation

309 To assess transferability, the model is trained on one market (for example CZ) and tested on the
310 other (GR). Scaling statistics are recomputed locally to avoid data leakage, meaning that no
311 information from the test market is used during training or normalization. Performance is
312 evaluated on 2024-H2 using metrics that are standard in peak-demand and rare-event studies. For
313 hit-rate@ k , we sort hours by score and consider the top $k\%$ of hours as candidate DR windows.
314 Let $y_t \in \{0,1\}$ indicate whether an hour belongs to a high-price or high-ramp event, and T_k be the
315 index set of the top $k\%$ hours by score. The hit-rate is calculated as follows:

$$316 \quad \text{Hit-rate@}k = \frac{1}{|T_k|} \sum_{t \in T_k} y_t \quad (10)$$

317 which measures the precision of DR timing in the most critical fraction of hours, according to
318 the hit-rate definitions for peak prediction and timestamping in building energy demand and
319 peak-load reviews [34]. Precision-Recall and average precision (AP) used for anomaly and spike
320 detection in energy data and electricity price, are reported in [35]. In addition, lead-time
321 distributions and coverage under conformal calibration are examined. For each event with start

322 time t_{event} and the first preceding alert time t_{alert} within a look-back window, the lead-time, l is
323 expressed in hours:

$$324 \quad l = \max(0, t_{\text{event}} - t_{\text{alert}}) \quad (11)$$

325 As a baseline, we benchmark against static rule-based thresholds such as price and ramp
326 percentiles and compare their hit-rate, AP, and lead-time statistics with the state-aware approach.

327 4 Results

328 4.1 Market-state discovery

329 A two-dimensional embedding of the 48-hour windows is used to examine structural patterns in
330 the CZ and GR electricity markets prior to applying regime labels. The embedding is obtained by
331 applying PCA to the learned feature representations produced by the self-supervised encoder. In
332 this map, each point represents one 48-hour window of joint load, forecast, and price. Points that
333 sit close together correspond to windows with similar time patterns and similar combinations of
334 load, ramps, and prices, while points that are far apart represent very different operating
335 conditions. The two axes (Embedding 1 and Embedding 2) are latent components without
336 physical units, but broad regions of the map can be read as typical operating regimes such as
337 high-load evening peaks or low-load mid-day solar periods.

338 Figure 2. State Map by Country. Two-dimensional embedding of 48-hour market windows for
339 Czech Republic (CZ, blue) and Greece (GR, orange); each point is a window, colored by
340 country.
341

342 Figure 2 presents the joint state map for both markets. CZ windows form a compact cluster
343 concentrated on the positive side of Embedding 1, indicating relatively homogeneous load-price
344 dynamics. GR windows appear more dispersed, extending further along the negative direction of

345 Embedding 1 and exhibiting a wider spread across both axes. This suggests that GR experiences
346 greater variability in the coupling between load, ramps, and prices. The partial overlap between
347 the two clusters indicates the presence of shared underlying regimes, although differences in
348 centroid location and dispersion point to structural contrasts in diurnal patterns, ramp intensity,
349 and volatility profiles.

350 Figure 3 provides separate density maps for each country. CZ exhibits a tight, high-density
351 core, consistent with stable and recurring operating conditions. GR shows a broader and more
352 diffuse density structure with heavier tails, reflecting more diverse system conditions and a larger
353 share of stressed or transitional windows. These distributional differences highlight that the two
354 markets exhibit different regime frequencies and variability levels despite sharing similar daily
355 market structures.

356
357 Figure 3. State Map by Country — Density. Hexbin density plots of 48-hour market windows for
358 Czech Republic (CZ, left) and Greece (GR, right), derived from PCA embeddings.

359 Figure 4. State Map with Regimes. Two-dimensional embedding of 48-hour market windows
 360 clustered into three regimes: *normal* (blue), *ramping* (orange), and *volatile* (green). Cluster
 361 centroids are marked with × and 95% confidence ellipses outline regime boundaries.
 362

363
 364 Figure 4 introduces the three learned regimes: normal, ramping, and volatile. The normal
 365 regime forms a compact region associated with stable price–load behaviour. The ramping regime
 366 shifts downward along Embedding 2 and represents windows with strong gradients in price or
 367 load. The volatile regime forms the most dispersed region and contains windows characterized
 368 by heightened variability and instability. Although some overlap exists at the regime boundaries,
 369 the overall structure shows clear differentiation, indicating that the embedding captures
 370 meaningful operational states relevant for DR timing.

371 Overall, CZ displays more concentrated and predictable market states, whereas GR presents
 372 greater dispersion and a higher prevalence of ramping and volatile windows. The regime map
 373 formalizes these patterns, providing the foundation for state-aware DR scoring evaluated in
 374 Sections 4.2 and 4.3.

375 4.2 Performance of state-aware DR windows

376 **Table 1** reports the precision (hit-rate) of the state-aware and static threshold methods at
 377 different top-k% cutoffs for identifying high-price and high-ramping windows. For both markets
 378 and both event types, the static threshold approach achieves the highest precision, particularly at
 379 the most extreme cutoff (Top-5%). Price spikes are strongly concentrated in the upper tail of the
 380 price distribution, enabling the static method to reach perfect precision at the Top-5% and remain

381 above 0.94 at the Top-10%. The state-aware method performs more moderately (0.67–0.72),
 382 since regime-based scoring captures broader operating conditions rather than targeting only the
 383 largest magnitude deviations. A similar pattern holds for ramping events: static thresholds
 384 provide near-perfect precision at the Top-5%, whereas the state-aware method performs
 385 substantially lower due to the more diffuse nature of ramping behaviour.

386
 387 Table 1. Hit-rate (precision) of state-aware vs. static threshold methods for identifying high-price
 388 and high-ramping windows. Values show precision at different top-k% cut-offs (5, 10, 20%).

k%	High Price Windows – State-aware	High Price Windows – Static threshold	High Ramping Windows – State-aware	High Ramping Windows – Static threshold
5	0.7158	1.0000	0.2619	1.0000
10	0.6717	0.9454	0.3127	0.5437
20	0.3857	0.5009	0.2447	0.3935

389 Figure 5 visualizes these differences, showing that static thresholds dominate at all k-levels.
 390 The gap narrows at larger k% values, indicating that regime information becomes more effective
 391 when the objective is to identify a broader set of stressed periods rather than only the most
 392 extreme events.

393
 394 Figure 5. Hit-rate at Top-k% for high-price (left) and high-ramping (right) windows using state-
 395 aware and static threshold methods.

396
 397 Figure 6. Precision–Recall curves for high-price (left) and high-ramping (right) windows under
 398 state-aware and static detection.

399 Figure 6 presents the Precision–Recall (PR) curves for high-price and high-ramping
 400 windows. For high-price events, the static method achieves very high precision across nearly the
 401 full recall range ($AP = 0.994$), confirming that price spikes are tightly concentrated in the upper
 402 tail. The state-aware method yields lower overall precision ($AP = 0.507$), as latent regimes
 403 capture structural patterns but do not fully reflect the extremity of price excursions. For ramping
 404 events, both methods perform worse than in the price case; however, the static method again
 405 achieves much stronger discrimination ($AP = 0.718$ vs. 0.180). This reflects that ramping
 406 behaviour is more irregular and less strongly aligned with the latent regimes.

407 Overall, the results indicate that static thresholding is more effective for identifying the
 408 highest-severity price and ramp events, while the state-aware model contributes through
 409 anticipatory detection rather than peak-event precision. The early-warning value of state-aware
 410 signals is analysed in Section 4.3.

411 4.3 Lead-time advantages

412 Figure 7 presents the empirical cumulative distribution of lead-times for state-aware and static
 413 DR signals over a 24-hour horizon. Lead-time refers to the number of hours between the alert
 414 and the start of a high-price or high-ramping window. For both event types, the state-aware
 415 curves rise earlier than the static curves, indicating that regime-based alerts anticipate stressed
 416 conditions before the underlying variables reach extreme values. Although both methods
 417 eventually issue alerts before nearly all events, the state-aware method consistently identifies
 418 emerging stress conditions earlier across the full temporal range. This pattern suggests that
 419 regime information supports not only short-term operational responses but also medium-horizon
 420 decisions involving storage dispatch, load shifting, and bidding strategies.

421
422 Figure 7. Cumulative distribution of lead-time for state-aware and static DR signals across price
423 and ramping events. Lead-time refers to how early the DR signal is issued before the
424 corresponding high-price or high-ramping window.
425

426 Table 2. Lead-time performance of state-aware vs. static detection methods. $\Delta = \text{State-aware} -$
427 Static (in hours) .

Task	Metric	State-aware (h)	Static (h)	Δ (h)
Price	Mean	5.45	2.92	+2.53
Price	Median	6.00	2.00	+4.00
Ramp	Mean	5.70	4.37	+1.33
Ramp	Median	6.00	6.00	0.00

428
429 **Table 2** summarizes the lead-time performance. For high-price events, the state-aware
430 method provides substantially earlier warning. The mean lead-time increases from 2.92 h under
431 the static rule to 5.45 h with regime-based detection ($\Delta = +2.53$ h), and the median increases
432 from 2 h to 6 h ($\Delta = +4$ h). These improvements indicate that extreme price surges tend to evolve
433 from identifiable volatile market states that appear several hours in advance, enabling earlier
434 anticipation when using latent regime information.

435 For ramping events, the gains are more modest. The mean lead-time improves from 4.37 h to
436 5.70 h ($\Delta = +1.33$ h), while the median remains unchanged at 6 h. This suggests that high-ramp
437 episodes arise from a broader variety of operating conditions and exhibit weaker alignment with
438 specific latent regimes. As a result, state-aware detection improves ramp anticipation only
439 marginally.

440
441 Figure 8. Lead-time distributions for high-price and high-ramping events using state-aware and
442 static detection methods.

443 Figure 8 provides violin plots of the lead-time distributions. For high-price events, the state-
444 aware method produces a concentrated distribution near the upper bound (5–6 h), while the static
445 distribution is broader and centered much lower, confirming the large median improvement
446 reported in Table 2. For ramping events, both distributions cluster near 6 h, and the difference
447 between the methods is small. Although the state-aware approach shows slightly higher density
448 in the upper range, the overall shapes are similar, reflecting the limited connection between ramp
449 events and specific latent regimes.

450 Overall, these results demonstrate that regime-based DR signals offer clear early-warning
451 advantages for high-price events, where extreme conditions tend to emerge from well-defined
452 volatile states. For ramping events, the benefits are more limited due to their more diffuse and
453 heterogeneous origins.

454 4.4 Cross-market transferability

455 Table 3 reports the transfer performance of the state-aware and static DR scoring methods
456 between CZ and GR. The state-aware approach maintains a substantial portion of its predictive
457 skill when applied to the opposite market. Depending on the task and transfer direction, the state-
458 aware signals retain between 46.7% and 214.2% of their in-sample Average Precision (AP). This
459 indicates that the latent regime structure captures system characteristics that are partly invariant
460 across the two markets.

461 Table 3. Transfer performance (AP) of state-aware and static DR signals between CZ and GR

Task	Train→Test	AP (state)	AP (static)	Baseline_in_train (AP)	Retention (%)
PRICE	CZ→GR	0.441	1.000	0.579	76.2
PRICE	GR→CZ	0.579	1.000	0.441	131.2
RAMP	CZ→GR	0.270	1.000	0.126	214.2
RAMP	GR→CZ	0.126	1.000	0.270	46.7

462 Static thresholding, by contrast, achieves $AP \approx 1.000$ within each market because extreme
463 price and ramp events lie in the far upper tail of the respective distributions. However, this
464 behaviour does not transfer across markets: static rules rely entirely on market-specific

465 thresholds and therefore provide no useful discriminative ability outside the market where they
466 are calibrated. These results show that regime-based scoring has meaningful cross-market
467 generalization, while static percentile-based methods remain strictly local to each system.

468 4.5 Risk control via conformal calibration

469 To keep the alerting policy robust under uncertainty and non-stationarity, conformal calibration
470 is applied to the state-aware scores. For a chosen risk tolerance α the procedure selects a score
471 threshold such that the probability of missing a true high-risk window remains below the target
472 level. The resulting reliability curve in Figure 9 compares the desired coverage $1-\alpha$ with the
473 empirical coverage on a held-out test set.

474
475

Figure 9. Reliability of Risk-Controlled Alerts via Conformal Calibration.

476 For price events, the calibrated state-aware alerts achieve coverage at or above the target in
477 the operational range between 0.75 and 0.90. Coverage is slightly conservative at lower targets
478 and approaches 1.0 as the target moves towards 0.90, indicating that most high-price events are
479 captured by the calibrated rule. For ramping events, the curve is steeper, with coverage rising
480 sharply in the 0.90–0.95 range and remaining close to the ideal diagonal near typical reliability
481 levels.

482 These results indicate that conformal calibration maintains valid risk control for both event
483 types under temporal variability. These guarantees hold without retraining or hyperparameter
484 adjustment, which makes the method suitable for operational use in environments subject to
485 distribution shifts and cross-market deployment.

486 5 Discussion

487 The results illustrate how self-supervised state embeddings can uncover meaningful structure in
488 electricity market dynamics. The discovered regimes align with operational patterns observed in

489 both systems—such as winter evening peaks, mid-day solar dip periods caused by high PV
490 generation, and clusters of price or load volatility, which enhances the interpretability of the
491 model for system operators.

492 A key insight is the trade-off between detection accuracy and early warning. Static thresholds
493 consistently achieve the highest hit-rate and AP values for the most extreme price and ramp
494 events. However, these gains come at the cost of reactive timing, with alerts typically occurring
495 only when values have already crossed extreme thresholds. In contrast, state-aware alerts are less
496 precise but substantially earlier, enabling operators to adjust schedules, activate storage, or plan
497 flexibility actions several hours ahead. This dual behavior suggests a hybrid operational strategy:
498 use static thresholds for extreme near-term actions and state-aware alerts for anticipatory
499 scheduling.

500 Cross-market transferability results show that embeddings learned in one country retain 46-
501 214% of their predictive value when applied to the other. This suggests that the latent regimes
502 reflect underlying structural characteristics of European electricity systems, including shared
503 load shapes, renewable intermittency, and price–demand interactions. These features make the
504 approach promising for broader regional DR coordination under the EU Internal Energy Market.
505 Conformal calibration provides a reliable guarantee on alert coverage without retraining, even
506 under volatility shifts. This highlights a key operational advantage: system operators can deploy
507 the model in environments with evolving market conditions while maintaining explicit risk
508 bounds.

509 However, limitations remain. Intraday price data are sparse for both markets, restricting the
510 analysis to day-ahead conditions. Also, weather variables and renewable generation profiles were
511 not included, which may further enhance state discovery. Finally, the study is limited to two
512 markets; validation in additional EU regions with higher VRE penetration would strengthen
513 generalizability.

514 6 Conclusion

515 This study examined a state-aware framework for timing demand response interventions
516 using self-supervised market-state embeddings, regime-based scoring, and conformal risk
517 control. The analysis for the Czech Republic and Greece showed that latent regimes derived
518 from multivariate 48-hour windows capture meaningful patterns in joint load–price dynamics
519 and differentiate normal, ramping, and volatile operating conditions.

520 Static percentile-based thresholds remained the most effective tool for pinpointing the most
521 extreme price and ramp events, achieving the highest hit-rate and Average Precision. However,
522 regime-based alerts consistently provided earlier warning, particularly for high-price episodes,
523 with gains of up to 2.5 hours in mean lead-time and 4 hours in median lead-time. These results
524 indicate that state-aware signals are well suited for anticipatory scheduling and flexibility
525 planning, while static thresholds are better suited to very short-term emergency actions.

526 Cross-market experiments demonstrated that state-aware signals retain a substantial fraction
527 of their predictive power when transferred between the two markets, whereas static thresholds
528 did not generalize beyond the market in which they were calibrated. This suggests that the
529 learned regimes capture structural features that are shared across European power systems.
530 Conformal calibration further ensured that alert coverage remained close to nominal targets
531 without retraining, providing a transparent and statistically grounded risk-control layer.

532 Future research should extend the framework to include intraday markets, high-resolution
533 weather and renewable generation data, and additional European power systems with different
534 market designs and higher VRE shares. Integration with real-world DR programmes and
535 practical market interfaces would provide a more complete assessment of operational value and
536 user acceptance.

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552 **Data statement**

553 The dataset used in this study is openly available on Zenodo under a CC BY 4.0 license at
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555 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

556 **Ohn Zin Lin:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation, software,
557 Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration. **Libor Štěpanec:** Methodology,
558 Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Eftichios Koutroulis:** Validation, Writing
559 – review & editing, Supervision. **Juchelkova Dagmar:** Funding acquisition, Writing – review &
560 editing, Supervision. **Hnin Yee Aye:** Data curation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing.

561 **References**

- 562 [1] Lu R, Bai R, Huang Y, Li Y, Jiang J, Ding Y. Data-driven real-time price-based demand response for
563 industrial facilities energy management. *Applied Energy* 2021;283:116291.
564 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.116291>.

- 565 [2] Sinsel SR, Riemke RL, Hoffmann VH. Challenges and solution technologies for the integration of
566 variable renewable energy sources—a review. *Renewable Energy* 2020;145:2271–85.
567 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2019.06.147>.
- 568 [3] Rouholamini M, Wang C, Nehrir H, Hu X, Hu Z, Aki H, et al. A Review of Modeling, Management,
569 and Applications of Grid-Connected Li-Ion Battery Storage Systems. *IEEE Trans Smart Grid*
570 2022;13:4505–24. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSG.2022.3188598>.
- 571 [4] Wohlfarth K, Klobasa M, Gutknecht R. Demand response in the service sector – Theoretical,
572 technical and practical potentials. *Applied Energy* 2020;258:114089.
573 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.114089>.
- 574 [5] Papingiotis T, Korres DN, Koulocheris V, Koronaki IP, Papaefthimiou VD. A comparative
575 performance study of concentrating PV/T and ETC for solar adsorption cooling system in Greece.
576 *Renewable Energy* 2025;251:123395. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2025.123395>.
- 577 [6] Kubín A, Knápek J, Koltsaklis N. A long-term energy transition planning model for a district heating
578 and cooling sector incorporating sector coupling approach: A case study of the Czech district
579 heating and cooling sector. *Energy Conversion and Management* 2025;341:120058.
580 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2025.120058>.
- 581 [7] Pechancová V, Pavelková D, Saha P. Community Renewable Energy in the Czech Republic: Value
582 Proposition Perspective. *Front Energy Res* 2022;10:821706.
583 <https://doi.org/10.3389/ferg.2022.821706>.
- 584 [8] Shi R, Jiao Z. Individual household demand response potential evaluation and identification based
585 on machine learning algorithms. *Energy* 2023;266:126505.
586 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2022.126505>.
- 587 [9] Wang F, Lu X, Chang X, Cao X, Yan S, Li K, et al. Household profile identification for behavioral
588 demand response: A semi-supervised learning approach using smart meter data. *Energy*
589 2022;238:121728. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.121728>.
- 590 [10] Haugen M, Blaisdell-Pijuan PL, Botterud A, Levin T, Zhou Z, Belsnes M, et al. Power market models
591 for the clean energy transition: State of the art and future research needs. *Applied Energy*
592 2024;357:122495. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.122495>.
- 593 [11] Skoczkowski T, Bielecki S, Wołowicz M, Sobczak L, Węglarz A, Gilewski P. Participation in demand
594 side response. Are individual energy users interested in this? *Renewable Energy* 2024;232:121104.
595 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2024.121104>.
- 596 [12] O'Connor C, Bahloul M, Rossi R, Prestwich S, Visentin A. Conformal Prediction for electricity price
597 forecasting in the day-ahead and real-time balancing market. *Energy and AI* 2025;21:100571.
598 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyai.2025.100571>.
- 599 [13] Li X, Deng J, Liu J. A two-layer and three-stage dynamic demand response game model considering
600 the out of sync response for gases generators. *Renewable Energy* 2024;228:120681.
601 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2024.120681>.
- 602 [14] Fleschutz M, Bohlayer M, Braun M, Henze G, Murphy MD. The effect of price-based demand
603 response on carbon emissions in European electricity markets: The importance of adequate carbon
604 prices. *Applied Energy* 2021;295:117040. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.117040>.
- 605 [15] Bâra A, Georgescu IA, Oprea S-V. The role of generation mix, demand fluctuations and sequential
606 markets in shaping intraday electricity prices. Evidence from Romania. *Renewable Energy*
607 2025;255:123782. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2025.123782>.
- 608 [16] Zhao S, Zhou X, Jin M, Hou Z, Yang C, Li Z, et al. Rethinking self-supervised learning for time series
609 forecasting: A temporal perspective. *Knowledge-Based Systems* 2024;305:112652.
610 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2024.112652>.
- 611 [17] Koltsaklis NE, Knápek J. Integrated market scheduling with flexibility options. *Renewable and*
612 *Sustainable Energy Reviews* 2025;208:115020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2024.115020>.

- 613 [18] Wei Y, Fan J, Meng Q, Debnath KB, Yang Y, Liu J, et al. EOLD: A reinforcement learning-based
614 energy-optimised load disaggregation framework for demand-side energy management.
615 Renewable Energy 2025;252:123536. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2025.123536>.
- 616 [19] Wu S, Pang A. Two-stage optimal scheduling strategy for community integrated energy system
617 based on uncertainty and integrated demand response model. Renewable Energy
618 2025;251:123373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2025.123373>.
- 619 [20] Chuliá H, Klein T, Muñoz Mendoza JA, Uribe JM. Vulnerability of European electricity markets: A
620 quantile connectedness approach. Energy Policy 2024;184:113862.
621 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2023.113862>.
- 622 [21] Bai J, Ding T, Jia W, Mu C, Siano P, Shahidehpour M. Battery Charging and Swapping System
623 Involved in Demand Response for Joint Power and Transportation Networks. IEEE Trans Intell
624 Transport Syst 2024;25:6836–47. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2023.3346403>.
- 625 [22] He M, Khorsand M. Behavior-aware assessment of demand response participation in power
626 systems using causal artificial intelligence. Electric Power Systems Research 2024;237:110981.
627 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epsr.2024.110981>.
- 628 [23] Sloot D, Lehmann N, Ardone A. Explaining and promoting participation in demand response
629 programs: The role of rational and moral motivations among German energy consumers. Energy
630 Research & Social Science 2022;84:102431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102431>.
- 631 [24] Sridhar A, Honkapuro S, Ruiz F, Stoklasa J, Annala S, Wolff A, et al. Residential consumer
632 preferences to demand response: Analysis of different motivators to enroll in direct load control
633 demand response. Energy Policy 2023;173:113420. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2023.113420>.
- 634 [25] Lago J, Marcjasz G, De Schutter B, Weron R. Forecasting day-ahead electricity prices: A review of
635 state-of-the-art algorithms, best practices and an open-access benchmark. Applied Energy
636 2021;293:116983. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.116983>.
- 637 [26] Dong Y, Li Z, Zhang H, Wang C, Zhou X. Robust Coordinated Planning of Multi-Region Integrated
638 Energy Systems With Categorized Demand Response. IEEE Trans Smart Grid 2024;15:5678–92.
639 <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSG.2024.3432750>.
- 640 [27] Chen Y, Wang Y, Kirschen D, Zhang B. Model-Free Renewable Scenario Generation Using
641 Generative Adversarial Networks. IEEE Trans Power Syst 2018;33:3265–75.
642 <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2018.2794541>.
- 643 [28] ENTSO-E. ENTSO-E Transparency Platform. European Network of Transmission System Operators
644 for Electricity (ENTSO-E) 2025. <https://transparency.entsoe.eu/>.
- 645 [29] Rodríguez E, Cardemil JM, Droguett EL. Developing temporal clustering for identifying solar
646 radiation zones to improve separation models. Renewable Energy 2026;256:123809.
647 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2025.123809>.
- 648 [30] Xu X, Cao Q, Deng R, Guo Z, Chen Y, Yan J. A cross-dataset benchmark for neural network-based
649 wind power forecasting. Renewable Energy 2025;254:123463.
650 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2025.123463>.
- 651 [31] Przewięźlikowski M, Pyla M, Zieliński B, Twardowski B, Tabor J, Śmieja M. Augmentation-aware
652 self-supervised learning with conditioned projector. Knowledge-Based Systems 2024;305:112572.
653 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2024.112572>.
- 654 [32] Barber RF, Candès EJ, Ramdas A, Tibshirani RJ. Predictive inference with the jackknife+. Ann Statist
655 2021;49. <https://doi.org/10.1214/20-AOS1965>.
- 656 [33] Xu C, Xie Y. Conformal Prediction for Time Series. IEEE Trans Pattern Anal Mach Intell
657 2023;45:11575–87. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.2023.3272339>.
- 658 [34] Zhao M, Gomez-Rosero S, Nouraei H, Zych C, Capretz MAM, Sadhu A. Toward Prediction of Energy
659 Consumption Peaks and Timestamping in Commercial Supermarkets Using Deep Learning. Energies
660 2024;17:1672. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en17071672>.

661 [35] Himeur Y, Ghanem K, Alsalemi A, Bensaali F, Amira A. Artificial intelligence based anomaly
662 detection of energy consumption in buildings: A review, current trends and new perspectives.
663 Applied Energy 2021;287:116601. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.116601>.